

DIGITAL LABORATORIES AS A MEANS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF NATURAL SCIENCES

¹Boyazidkhon Sultonov, ²Asadjon Nosirkulov

¹Teacher at Tashkent State Transport University, ²Teacher at Tashkent State University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14169330>

Abstract. This article examines the role of digital laboratories and simulators in improving the quality of education in the field of natural sciences. Using the example of the PhET simulation, the possibilities that they open up for students are discussed, allowing them to visualize complex concepts and actively participate in learning. The study shows that such technologies contribute to a better understanding of educational material and increase students' interest in subjects. The article also highlights the importance of introducing digital laboratories into the educational process in Uzbekistan in order to meet modern educational requirements and standards

Keywords: Digital laboratory, improving the quality of education, PhET modeling, resources for students

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tabiiy fanlar sohasida ta'lim sifatini oshirishda raqamli laboratoriyalar va simulyatorlarning roli ko'rib chiqilgan. PhET simulyatsiyasi misolidan foydalanib, ular talabalar uchun ochadigan imkoniyatlar muhokama qilinadi, bu ularga murakkab tushunchalarni tasavvur qilish va o'rganishda faol ishtirok etish imkonini beradi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, bunday texnologiyalar o'quv materialini yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi va talabalarning fanlarga qiziqishini oshiradi. Maqolada, shuningdek, zamonaviy ta'lim talablari va standartlariga javob beradigan raqamli laboratoriyalarni O'zbekistonda o'quv jarayoniga joriy etish muhimligi ta'kidlangan

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli laboratoriyalar, ta'lim sifatini oshirish, PhET simulyatsiyalari, talabalar uchun resurslar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль цифровых лабораторий и симуляторов в повышении качества образования в области естественных наук. На примере моделирования PhET обсуждаются возможности, которые они открывают для студентов, позволяя им визуализировать сложные концепции и активно участвовать в обучении. Исследование показывает, что такие технологии способствуют лучшему пониманию учебного материала и повышают интерес учащихся к предметам. В статье также подчеркивается важность внедрения цифровых лабораторий в образовательный процесс в Узбекистане с целью соответствия современным образовательным требованиям и стандартам

Ключевые слова: Цифровая лаборатория, повышающие качество образования, моделирование PhET, ресурсы для студентов

Introduction: In the modern world, higher education faces many challenges, especially in the field of natural sciences. Teachers strive not only to transfer knowledge, but also to prepare students for the real conditions of work in science and technology. However, traditional laboratory work has its limitations: the high cost of equipment, the danger of some experiments and inaccessibility for students, especially in remote regions. In this context, digital laboratories and simulators such as PhET Interactive Simulations are becoming indispensable tools for improving the educational process and strengthening students' knowledge.

The main part: PhET Interactive Simulations is a platform that provides free interactive simulations for teaching physics, chemistry, biology and other natural sciences. These simulations allow students to conduct experiments and observe the results in real time. These are not just virtual "toys", but powerful educational tools that make learning more fun and understandable. PhET simulations are widely used in various countries, including the United States, Japan and etc. The popularity of this platform is due to its intuitive design, which engages students at all levels — from elementary school to university. PhET helps students visualize complex scientific concepts, making them more understandable and accessible to study. For example, in a physics course, students can use simulation. One of the striking examples of the use of digital laboratories in teaching natural sciences is the study of Kepler's laws. The PhET "Orbits" simulation allows students to visualize and explore the movements of planets around the Sun based on Kepler's three laws. Students can change parameters such as speed and distance from the Sun to observe how these changes affect the orbits of the planets. Students can collect data on orbital periods and orbital radii, which allows them to verify Kepler's law of harmonies. The simulation provides visual data on the motion of the planets, which helps students better understand the concepts of gravity and orbital motion. For teachers, using PhET simulations allows:

1. To simplify the explanation of complex concepts: Visual elements help students to better assimilate the material.
2. Increase student engagement: Interactive classes promote greater interest in the topics being studied.
3. Provide flexibility in learning: Teachers can adapt classes to different levels of students' knowledge, providing an opportunity for individual learning.

In addition to PhET, there are other applications that are successfully implemented in the educational process all over the world, then we will write about them in brief: **1. Beyond Labz** - This platform offers virtual laboratories in chemistry, physics and biology. It provides users with the opportunity to conduct experiments in a secure environment, which makes it ideal for remote learning. **2. Virtual Physics Laboratory (VPLab)** - This application offers a variety of physics simulations, allowing students to explore various physical phenomena. VPLab helps you visualize complex concepts and makes learning more accessible. **3. Interactive Physics (Design Simulation Technologies)** - This program allows students to simulate physical phenomena and create their own experiments. It develops critical thinking and promotes a deeper understanding of physics.

Using Kepler's Laws Simulation

The integration of applications such as PhET into the educational system of Uzbekistan can significantly improve the quality of education. Here are some reasons why such tools should be implemented more widely: **Increased engagement:** Interactive simulations can better attract students' attention compared to traditional methods. They allow students to experiment and explore scientific concepts in a virtual environment, contributing to a deeper understanding. **Resource Availability:** PhET provides free access to a wide range of simulations, which makes high-quality educational materials available to students regardless of their financial capabilities. This is especially important in regions where educational resources may be limited. **Support for different learning styles:** The visual and interactive nature of the simulations matches different learning preferences, which helps visual and kinesthetic learners to master concepts more easily. **Flexibility in learning environments:** PhET can be used in a variety of settings — traditional classrooms, online courses, or hybrid models, making it adaptable to different educational needs and circumstances.

At a time when many countries are actively introducing or have introduced digital technologies into the educational process, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to use these tools to improve the quality of education. The integration of PhET and other digital laboratories into higher education will improve students' understanding of physics and other natural sciences, preparing them for future challenges in a globalized world. This will not only improve the quality of science teaching, but also make education more accessible to students in various regions of the country.

Conclusion. Digital laboratories are a powerful tool for improving the quality of science teaching. Their use not only strengthens students' knowledge, but also develops practical skills necessary for a successful career in science and technology. In the context of the rapid development of science and technology, it is important to continue to introduce innovative approaches to education in order to prepare competitive specialists capable of solving complex problems of the future.

References

1. Boyazidkhon Sulstonov, (2024) "Programming as a physics teaching tool"
2. Dareen Shukri A. Alnaser, Sufian Forawi, "Investigating the Effects of Virtual Laboratories on Students' Motivation and Attitudes Toward Science"
3. Baird, J. R. (2019). "Using PhET Simulations to Enhance Learning in Science Education." *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 28(2), 145-158.
4. Dubé, M., & Dubé, É. (2017). "Evaluating the Impact of PhET Simulations on Student Understanding of Physics Concepts." *Physics Teacher*, 55(8), 516-521.